

Laughter in Japanese sound performances as a shared conceptual point

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Abstract

Some remarkable Japanese sound artists of the 21st century share conceptual links with earlier artists like Group Ongaku, Taj Mahal Travelers, and Akio Suzuki who began their activities in the 1960s. Presenting *Methodicism (Hoho-shugi)*, a group of Japanese media artists including Masahiro Miwa, this paper will discuss a sense of laughter as a key concept.

Miwa defines Reverse-simulation music in terms of three aspects: rule-based generation, interpretation, and naming. For Miwa, Reverse-simulation music is the only feasible and practical way to restore “discipline” in contemporary music. Restoring “discipline” is a serious artistic topic as well as an absurd rule which regulates human bodies. The performance based on unhuman rules leads to sense of laughter.

Motoharu Kawashima asserts that laughter is the foundation of human culture, citing Aristotle’s words. This concept forms the basis of Kawashima’s action music, which means focusing on consideration of what actions are involved in producing that sound rather than focusing on what kind of sound will ultimately be produced.

Both the reversed situation in Miwa and the deviation of meaning in Kawashima led to laughter from the audience, and the composers searched for laughter as backbone of their art.

A sense of laughter has been accepted by the next generation of Japanese sound artists. Taro Yasuno developed three series of works: Search Engine, MISUCINEMA, and Zombie Music. All three evoke laughter due to the simplicity and absurdity of the performers' actions. Yasuno’s Zombie system is a conceptual instrument that critiques the relationship between technology and the human body in the present day. Zombie Music is highly developed and effective system for visualizing the physical labor necessary for sound production.

1. Introduction

1.1. sound performances in Japan

From the 1960s onwards, Japanese sound artists have developed unique styles in technology-based performances; searching for sounds through improvisation with electronic gadgets, creating rules to mechanically control the human body, revealing the process of experiments, and setting system for communication with current technology. These artists share a spirit of exploration, searching for new styles of sound generation and new types of time-space

experience with conceptually modified technology. On the way to find new styles, artists also created some special type of communication appealing to sense of humor or some other emotions.

One of Japanese Fluxus artists, Mieko Shiomi indicated a phase of laughter in their avant-garde performance such as Shiomi's *Direction Event* (1966) in the series of Spatial Poem. In the event, the pianist plays short phrases from a score divided into card-like sections, reads aloud the direction written on that card and then physically throws the card score in the indicated direction.

With the historical perspective since avant-garde humour, this article discusses Japanese sound-based performers in the last few decades, focusing especially on the phase of laughter or nonsense of experiments as aesthetics and concepts. As this paper targets the sound performances in the millennium which conceptually focuses on the relationship between technology and human body, it only slightly refers to the musical performances which do not take the up-to-date technological environments as the main conceptual theme of the piece even though they used recent digital developments.

The term <technology> covers quite vast range of sense and here I dare to limit to the practical digital environment for daily human life such as cell phone, internet, video streaming, digital communication tools from e-mail to SNS transmission tools. We can call it <artificial apparatus> in place of <technology>. Digital tools for creation or composition such as DAW or sound design software, or developing programs for sound composition are not necessarily the main discussive objects as for the Japanese history of conceptual base for sound performance.

1.2. Discussion framework

As the practical digital environment for daily use differs on the generation, I will not discuss the eminent achievements by the younger generations who mainly were born as internet-native, which demands the other perspective than those who are presented in this presentation. I will rather talk about the millennium works created by the composers who have been facing to the rapid evolution of musical live-performance and internet communication. While the technical developments share some common goals, conceptual aspect varies depending on each creator or on each composer, so the following discussions proceed with individual case from piece to piece, sharing the phase of <nonsense of experiments> and <laughter>.

Laughter as well as humor is one of essential human emotions both in daily life and in artistic representation. Laughter in Japanese indicates both the emotion or human action resulting from the emotion and the actions inducing the comical emotion. I'm not referring to the philosophical theory by Emmanuel Kant or Henry Bergson, but the social situation of the millennium in Japan, where the sub-culture trends include special booming of comic artists. Kimie Ohshima, Japanese sociolinguist, indicates that's the act of laughing is not solely for the person who is laughing, but that an act of conveying the message from one to the others. Laughter is indicating "I am happy to be with you", fostering a sense of connection with others and lifting the spirits of those around.¹ This communication, conveying the message to the others and sharing spirits, seems to be an essential element in Japanese sound performance. To communicate with the audience in a performance space, the artists has been creating their unique style of performance.

¹ Kimie Ohshima, 2006.

2. *Hoho machine* and Masahiro Miwa

2.1. Manifesto of *Hoho machine* 2000

I start with *Methodicism (Hoho-shugi)*, an art activist group, that started in 2000. The *Methodicist Manifesto (Hoho-shugi sengen)* was presented on January 1st 2000, under initiative of the visual artist Hideki Nakazawa (1963–). The performer and composer Tomomi Adachi (1972–) and the poet Shigeru Matsui (1975–) formed part of the group, and after two years, the composer Masahiro Miwa(1958-) also joined. Both Miwa and Matsui taught at IAMAS and strongly influenced the next generation of media artists such as Masatsune Yoshio(1972-), Yoshihisa Suzuki(1975-), Satoshi Fukushima(1977-), Taro Yasuno(1979-).

The *Manifesto of Ho-ho Machine* says:

Ho-ho machine (Method machine) is a system which can realize various types of arts understood as method arts and methodism including method picture, method poem and method music with the help of physical training. Human beings have gotten their special body as an art thanks to the trainings all through the history and the culture. And Ho-ho machine will, based on the idea of Hoho arts, realize new representations of physical practices which have been admitted as arts for now. Thus we will interpret all the paintings we draw as necessary for ourselves, all the poems we made as necessary for myself and all the music we composed as necessary for us., and we change them into physical trainings. Until now all the arts suppose the arts which is redefined in the history or in the culture. But Ho-ho machine dares to start from the zero level of cultural redefinition and aims at the apparition of new Hoho-Geijyitsu.²

2.2. *Hoho* and the rules designed by Masahiro Miwa

Pointing out from the manifest that the human body precipitates and that they impose new physical trainings on their bodies for realizing new representation and for re-defining arts. This type of re-definition can be found in the well-known *Reverse-simulation music* created by Masahiro Miwa, which had gotten the Golden Nica in Ars Electronica.

Gyaku-simulation (Reverse-simulation), a type of Method Music in which “phenomena verified in computer space are modelled in the real world in real space”. Miwa defines *Reverse-simulation music* in terms of three aspects: rule-based generation, interpretation, and naming. For Miwa, Reverse-simulation music is the only feasible and practical way to restore “discipline” in contemporary music.³

When discussing “artistic expression using apparatus”, we tend not to focus on the fact that we rely on the plugging of power distribution. Moreover, “beyond that electrical socket”—that is, behind the stable supply of electricity—lies an endless chain of globalised world problems: nuclear power plants, nuclear issues, oil interests, speculative capital, and indeed the wars in (the world.)⁴

² Hideki Nakazawa, 2000.

³ Masahiro Miwa, December 31,2004.

⁴ Preface in Masahiro Miwa,2023.

Admitting that he cannot confront against the huge problem behind the digital art, Miwa reflected the global ecological problems, doubted the political error and cynically represented the situation. The deep scepticism has changed to a sense of unity with his comrades; the sense which can be realized through some strict rules set by Miwa as a composer.

Three concepts can be inferred; Re-definition of arts, conscious of body which is compulsory separated from cultural background, global problem of ecology. The third one, global ecology, attracting many people, is connected to computer music through the electric plug as an apparatus. Power plugs and the immense electricity grid behind them are not usually something artists give much thought to. This mapping through artistic body can be presented as an art, and the apparatus is re-evaluated. Electricity and apparatus; representing the relation between technology and human.

Late in 2009, Miwa completed his declaration of Chubu Electric Power Art and emphasized, “electric energy has already become an integral part of our society, our thinking, and our very bodies” and that the situation is to be called as <electric civilization>. Miwa refers to the general creative output produced by the various audiovisual and computational devices arising from it as “expression involving/by means of apparatus (based of electricity)”. Miwa testifies that the Chubu Electric Power Art Declaration was conceived on Jyoji Yuasa's eightieth birthday in the presence of composer Yoriaki Matsudaira, and subsequently revised following criticism from Ryuichi Sakamoto.

Strict rules posed on human body and evidence-based approach to electric apparatus are developing furthermore and resulting into unexpected turn of events, which leads to the unique phase of laughter. This process can be indicated in Miwa's *Matarisama*, game like performance piece. The performance, based on Miwa's reverse-simulation rules, provokes sarcastic laughter from the audience. Miwa's signature work, titled *Matarisama*, reveals a sense of unity realized by sharing the strictly physical burdens. *Matarisama* was first performed at the Second Method Art Festival on 14 April 2002. The score for eight performers indicates that they should sit in a circle, facing the back of the performer in front of them. Each performer holds a bell in their right hand and a castanet in their left. The performers must follow the *suzukake* rules to maintain order, using either the bell or the castanets to tap the shoulder of the person in front of them after they have been tapped themselves. The performers should ring the bell by tapping the right shoulder of the player in front; and should play the castanets by tapping the left shoulder of the player in front.

The performers are forced to work hard, both physically and mentally, as they must repeatedly perform seemingly simple actions. Their bodies and actions are strictly controlled, compelling them to become machines that realize the rules. This reversed situation has a strong impact, as the performers take the seemingly absurd rules so seriously. This sometimes provokes laughter in the audience, who are in a safe and peaceful environment, safe in the knowledge that it is just a game.

The situation in which humans work like machines is a reverse of the normal situation, in which humans control machines. But Miwa introduces rules to reset the progress of *Matarisama*, enabling the performers, who were working together under strict rules, to develop a sense of unity. In case someone makes mistake, the rule-based chain of performance cycle stops and restarts. When the reversed cycle of the severe work chain stops and resets, a system of forgiveness and re-organization emerges among the performers. Here the audience finds the situation of forgiveness after laughable situation.

It's also possible to match this laughter as an humor defined by Emmanuel Kant, which arises from the “discrepancy” or “incongruity” between anticipated situations or logic and what actually occurs. The audience experiences discrepancy/ incongruity two times; anticipated some meaningful performance on the stage but it doesn't occur. This is the first gap, and the second gap occurs when the strict rules are liquidated by human error, which relieves the comrades as well as the audience.

3. Why people are laughing?

3.1. Kawashima's music as theatrical action

Even though the *suzukake* rules originate from computer calculations, XOR or exclusive OR, that is, the rules are based on digital calculations, *Matarisama* performance is given to the audience as a group practice by human body, which doesn't need computer electricity. So we can see it as the similar performance style as that of some theatrical pieces composed by Motoharu Kawashima, who calls his own performance as <enjiru ongaku> (music as theatrical action).

Even though Motoharu Kawashima has seldom created electroacoustic music, he shares sense of laughter with Miwa as the essential idea for the performance. Kawashima's action music is focusing on consideration of what actions are involved in producing the sound rather than focusing on what kind of sound will ultimately be produced.

According to Kawashima's statement, he is apparently influenced by John Cage, Vinko Globokar and Mauricio Kagel. Kawashima takes the way of searching further by asking how each parameter involved in a musical performance (fingering, breathing and tongue control for wind instruments). Performance can be re-evaluated in terms of how far it has strayed from tradition.

Defining the term <structure> both as musical formation (surface structure in Shenkerian usage) and as immanent time structure in musical piece, Kawashima describes <Structure of Laughter> as followings:

The structure of “suspension and its de-familiarization”, representative of the general structure of laughter, is both the temporal structure that elicits “laughter” and the structure that brings about the fulfilment of meaning in every moment. This can often be observed in classical music (particularly the music of J. Haydn), and a similar temporal structure can be identified in the music of Hermut Lachenmann and Jo Kondo. Furthermore that “mimicry becomes more interesting when accompanied by exaggeration” – is synonymous with finding “imitation” amusing, premised upon cultural consensus.⁵

Let's see some performance of Kawashima.

In *Das Lachenmann Ivb* (2017/2020 is a series of Kawashima's creation, materials of which are only direct laughter. It is a kind of category collection of human actions of laughing.

⁵ Motoharu Kawashima, 2020.

In the series of *Invention* explores the relationship between Japanese speech pronunciation and music. The speaker presents short conversation, and the ensemble imitates their intonations. In this way, speech is “learned” and can be spoken. The instrumental ensemble makes it sound “as though they were pronouncing them”.⁶

In *Polyprosopos I* (1995), for example, a series of phrase patterns are composed of the same pitch relations, which divides clearly each sound pattern. Each pattern reveals the same or different interval relations to those of the original linear structure. This context can reinforce or reverse the original nuances, sometimes engendering laughter because the modified musical nuances deprive the original of its meaning and deviate from the original phrases. Laughter in music has been discussed sometimes in the context performative effects. Kawashima identifies three structural elements in his music that are connected to laughter: the linear structure and simultaneous chords; the timbre-rhythm structure and polyphony; and the performing action and heterophony.

Both the reversed situation in Miwa and the deviation of meaning in Kawashima led to laughter from the audience, and the composers searched for laughter as the foundation of their art.

3.2. Nonsense experiment and personal representation

Miwa’s sense of humor is eminently found in the co-production as Formant Brothers with Nobuyasu Sakonda *Ordering Pizza*, in which MIDI keyboards equipped with formant synthesis system realizes real text pronunciation or conversation in order for ordering pizza delivery, and also in the piece with a paradoxical title <Non-real Traditional Art>, which is an imaginary folk music written with the tongue-in-cheek premise that if there were an island nation east of Japan. In *Ordering Pizza*, the audience were chuckling while hearing the unstable Japanese language but they applaud when the pizza is delivered to the performance venue.

Musicologist, Nobuhiro Ito, wrote <blend of wit and seriousness> is Miwa’s personality and essence of his works.⁷ In this saying, the humor of Miwa and that of Kawashima share the same effects, but laughter in Miwa’s performance results from discrepancy between algorithm and human, while laughter in Kawashima case realizes theatrical effects.

Conceptual network design by Miwa from logical algorithm to global perspective of electricity or fanatic ritual seemingly pretty personal and something like far-fetched. But people have accepted the personal fanaticism as totality of his personal representation.

Yojibei Yamazaki, a researcher of Miwa and his activities, describes Miwa’s singularity of mapping between three levels (music, generative rules, nomenclature) holds complexity of human reality and will survive even in AI society.

Music rooted in empathy with others, grounded in physicality and emotion, will remain distinctly human as long as they are understood as comprising three indispensable aspects – performance, generative rules, and naming”—rather than being reduced to mere sound manipulation equivalent solely to the “generation of rules” level within “reverse simulation music”.⁸

⁶ Motoharu Kawashima, 2022.

⁷ Nobuhiro Ito, 2016.

⁸ Yojibei Yamazaki, 2024.

4. From IAMAS and next generation

4.1. Taro Yasuno in ritual and robotics

Taro Yasuno, succeeding *Ho-ho machine* group from Miwa in November 2006, discovered a unique form of performance called *Search Engine* in which internet searches were used to generate music. *Search Engine* is more strongly linked to Yasuno's concept of performance and raises questions about modern society's dependence on internet communication. The work takes the form of a 'concert' as a social event, to be performed and realized by four performers and one pianist. The performers search for solo piano scores on Google and print out the scores successively as they appear in the listings returned. After printing, the performer loudly reads out the title of the piano piece and the composer's name. Then the pianist plays the piece. After playing the piece, the performer puts the score in a paper shredder. This process of searching for a piece, performing it, and then shredding the score is to be repeated for two hours.

Yasuno explains about the nonsense experiment that the piece criticises the situation where we repeatedly search for something through the search engine. It ignores the intention to select pieces by the pianist or the composer. Yasuno compares *Search Engine* with John Cage's concept of indeterminacy and defines that Google's search engine doesn't depend on chance but on the algorithm of a mega-company Google.

Another nonsense experiment by Yasuno, *MUSICCINEMA*, reveals live performance in which the performer improvises with mumbled and shouted fragments of words about things that they see in the movie on the stage screen. "Music Cinema III Nagoya" (2007), is a project piece for a solo performer, in which real-time voice sampling for multi-track recording works and is conceived for theatrical performance. The method of video editing is fit for real-time multi-track recording system: every time the same cut of movie appears, the performer newly verbalizes and shouts the image, and the sampled-voice in the previous cut overlays it.

In both *Search Engine* and *MUSICCINEMA*, the audience have experiences of special time and space with long and repetitive procedures of simple actions. These actions concern sound producing without intended time-structure and in this sense the pieces are sound performance. They can be possibly defined as exhibition style piece because the two performances doesn't have any decisive time design. In *MUSICCINEMA*, the condition is that a person follows the images, and the result is a personalized and fragmented contents which have no meaningful contexts. The audience laugh when they find the simple but absurd action repeated endlessly and that the performer keeps the operation(action) pretty seriously, such as a part of cog in the wheel.

In the recent performance of *DAIREIBYOU*,⁹ he droned on about mundane, uninspiring daily trifles in the movie projected on the screen. Musicologist Yuji Numano evaluates Yasuno's representation in a phrase "it's overwhelmingly brilliant because it is too dull."¹⁰ Twist from dullness becomes brilliancy in Yasuno's performance can be said to have similar structure as Miwa's mapping from strict rules to ethics for ecology or forgiveness in the community.

Yasuno's notorious signature series *Zombie Music* is highly developed playing-robots for visualizing the physical labor necessary for sound production. *Zombie Music* can be installation

⁹ Taro Yasuno, project description, <http://zombie.poino.net/>.

¹⁰ Yuji Numano, 2023.

as well as performance structure. *Zombie machine* developed by Yasuno does no more simulate human action. It pursues a “non-human” performance by eliminating the will and heart that invariably accompany human playing.¹¹ It contains a sense of humor and nihilism.

4.2. Motoki Ohkubo's audio-visual staging and space design

Motoki Ohkubo (1988–). started his artist career under influence of Miwa and recently he is highly evaluated by installations which connect technology and natural disaster like earthquake. Ohkubo’s piece by AI-composition thematizing playing the physical instrument includes *After School Session*, which is based on PONG (Atari, 1972), a classic arcade game and reconfigured as a sonic interface. The auto-playing by AI-controlled system gives impression of high-design media art, while some of his earlier sound performances include more humorous phase with low and high technology.¹²

Nonsense humor has another phase in *Harmonai-zou* (2015), for Gifu Salamanca Hall Tsuji-organ. Bricks for weights are placed on both the white and black keys in a one-octave range of the pedal keyboard, and changes in the sound are produced only by pulling the stops. The two performers ‘play’ the stop settings in time with a silent metronome, as notated in the score. In *sd.mod.live* (2018), Ohkubo uses two sampled video recordings of a performer playing a snare drum. The composer operates a PC while sitting between two screens where the sampled video recordings are shown. The sounds of the snare drum in the videos are modified in realtime and used to execute the real snares on the stage. Ohkubo writes that: “When the digitally modified sounds come from the real instruments, the audience watching the performing actions on the screens can feel that the digital representation is combined with our real world. The speaker—a device designed to deliver sound to the audience—was attached to a snare drum, thereby transforming the speaker into an apparatus for playing the instrument.”¹³

5. Conclusion and further discussion

In this presentation I have examined laughter in a trend in Japanese sound performance of the 21st century. I picked up 4 composers, three of whom worked or studied at IAMAS. They value laughter not only as a sign of affection or way to release tension, but also as a result of nonsense causality or a twist in the way in which different dimensions of communication are mapped. The strict rules are imposed on the body, defying predictions, and the gap between serious matters and absurdity etc. The audience shares the concentrated phase (trying to understand the rules, conceiving the strange situation, etc.) and experiences the sudden transition to the released phase. The stronger the audience’s concentration is, the more laughter is shared at the point of release. While both Miwa’s strict algorithm and Yasuno’s simple, stubborn rules conflict with human action, laughter provides a shared experience for human. The composers explore their own unique styles for this shared experience of laughter.

The future discussions should cover why laughter is shared in the artistic representation and whether this is related to the Japanese tradition of sound performance.

¹¹ Taro Yasuno, Miho Watanabe, description of the work, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YQUZf6nk7VM>.

¹² Motoki Ohkubo, project description, <https://motokiohkubo.net/projects/>.

¹³ Motoki Ohkubo, project description of *sd.mod.live*, <https://motokiohkubo.net/projects/2018/sd.mod.live/>.

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